

Thermal Decomposition and Powder X-Ray Diffraction Studies on Bis(phthalimido)-bis(morpholine) copper(II) Dihydrate

V. MISHRA* and M. C. JAIN**

Department of Post Graduate Studies in Chemistry, Nehru College, Chhibramau-209 721

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The synthesis and simultaneous TG, DTA and DTG studies of bis-(phthalimido)-bis(morpholine)copper(II) dihydrate have been performed. The X-ray diffraction data revealed the complex to have tetragonal unit cell with cell constants $a=4.482 \text{ \AA}$, $c=12.962 \text{ \AA}$. The final product of decomposition was confirmed by X-ray diffraction to be CuO. The isothermal dehydration of this complex was also studied at temperatures 180, 200, 225 and 250°. The kinetics of the isothermal dehydration follow a linear law with activation energy $94.50 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$.

THE thermal properties of metal complexes with organic reagents is one of the least studied aspects of coordination chemistry. Phthalimide and its derivatives have been the subject of considerable attention of many researchers because of their versatile uses in the fields of pharmacology¹⁻³, industries^{4,6} and analytical chemistry^{6,7}. Although a good deal of research work has been reported⁸⁻¹⁰ on the characterisation of the metal complexes of phthalimide, practically no attention has been devoted to the study of their thermal and isothermal decomposition. The present communication aims at the scheme of thermal decomposition of bis-(phthalimido)-bis(morpholine)copper(II) dihydrate, the kinetics of the isothermal dehydration of the complex, and the powder X-ray diffraction studies on different species which could be isolated at different decomposition stages.

Experimental

Phthalimide (Fluka AG) and morpholine (Sisco-Chem.) were used. All other chemicals were of AnalaR grade. The solvents (E. Merck, G. R.) were distilled twice and used without any further purification.

Powder X-ray patterns were recorded on a Philips PW-1140/90 X-ray diffractometer attached with digital, graphical and photographic assemblies using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ (1.5418 \AA) radiations at 12 mA and 32 kV. The thermal investigations were performed by means of a Paulik - Paulik and Erdey derivatograph (MOM, Hungary) at a heating rate of $8^\circ/\text{min}$ and chart speed 6 in/h in a platinum crucible in the atmosphere of air using calcined α -alumina as a reference material.

All other physical methods were the same as reported earlier⁹.

Bis(phthalimido)copper(II) tetrahydrate was prepared as reported earlier¹⁰.

Bis(phthalimido)bismorpholinecopper(II) dihydrate: A mixture of methanolic solutions of bis-phthalimidocopper(II) tetrahydrate and morpholine mixed in 1 : 2 molar ratio, was refluxed on a water-bath for 2-3 h with constant mechanical stirring. The resulting clear blue solution on slow evaporation gave bluish green complex which was filtered, washed with minimum quantities of methanol and dried at 70° (Found : Cu, 11.60 ; C, 51.00 ; H, 5.10 ; N, 9.85. $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{N})_2(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{ON})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires : Cu, 11.24 ; C, 50.92 ; H, 5.30 ; N, 9.90%).

Results and Discussion

Derivatographic studies: The combined TG, DTA and DTG curves of a 100 mg sample are depicted in Fig. 1. The decomposition scheme is given in Table 1. The complex is stable up to 180° after which the decomposition starts. The first step of decomposition is in the form of dehydration of the complex. The TG curve indicates a weight loss corresponding to two water molecules in the temperature range 180-250°. The DTA and DTG contain endothermic peaks at 200 and 210°, respectively. The single step dehydration of the complex in the form of two water molecules is an indication of the presence of these water molecules in the coordination sphere. The next step of decomposition is in the temperature range 280-330° in the decomposition of morpholine. The DTA curve shows two closely spaced endotherms at 300 and 320°. It reveals that this step of decomposition is

**Department of Physics, Nehru College, Chhibramau-209 721.

Fig. 1. TG, DTA and DTG curves for thermal decomposition of 100 mg of $[\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{N})_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{ON})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$.

actually a two-step decomposition and not a single-step one, as indicated by TG by a weight loss equivalent to two morpholine molecules in this region. In the temperature range 380–460° the phthalimide species are destroyed. This step of decomposition is observed as a big endothermic peak centred at 400° in DTA. An exothermic peak at 510° in DTA curve and the corresponding endothermic peak in DTG curve indicated complete decomposition of the complex and simultaneous oxidation of the products. The shape of DTA curve in the region 450–550° indicates that the oxidation of the decomposition products starts just after the destruction of the phthalimide species. Carbon monoxide

and nitric oxide which are the major products are oxidised, under the atmosphere of free air maintained within the instrument, to their respective higher oxides. The cupric oxide horizontal was obtained above 600°.

Powder X-ray diffraction studies : The patterns of the complex were analysed by Lipson's method¹¹. They could be successfully indexed for tetragonal crystal system. The results for $\sin^2\theta$ are depicted in Table 2.

Decomposition scheme	Temp. range °C	Weight loss % : Found/(Calcd.)
$[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{N})_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{ON})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$		
↓	180–250	6.40(6.38)
$[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{N})_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{ON})_2]$		
↓	280–330	33.00(32.86)
$[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$		
↓	380–460	77.95(77.63)
CuO + Lower oxides of carbon and nitrogen		
↓	460 onwards	—
CuO + Volatile higher oxides		

$\sin^2\theta$ (obs.)	$\sin^2\theta$ (calcd.)	I/I_0	Miller indices (hkl)
0.003 52	0.003 54	50	(001)
0.029 56	0.029 56	20	(100)
0.033 13	0.033 10	20	(101)
0.059 14	0.059 12	100	(110)
0.115 58	0.115 76	80	(114)
0.118 38	0.118 24	10	(200)
0.147 99	0.147 62	10	(115)
0.179 61	0.179 66	30	(213)
0.236 89	0.236 48	25	(220)
0.240 61	0.240 02	20	(221)
0.298 03	0.297 90	40	(303)
0.354 44	0.354 54	15	(305)

Lattice parameters : $a = 4.482 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 12.962 \text{ \AA}$.

Kinetics of isothermal dehydration: The kinetics of the dehydration were studied isothermally at 180, 200, 225 and 250°. At 180° the final product after 14 h of reaction was analysed and characterised. The X-ray diffraction pattern of the final product revealed that the observed d values and the corresponding intensities of the lines were in close agreement with the reported^{1,2} values for CuO. Samples were withdrawn from time to time to identify the intermediates formed. It was found by X-ray diffraction that no stable intermediate formed during the isothermal dehydration. The isothermal dehydration has been expressed in the form

$$\alpha = kT + C$$

where, k is the rate constant, T the time and C is the isothermal constant at different temperatures. The plots of α vs T at various temperatures gave straight lines (Fig. 2). The rate constants at 180, 200, 225 and 250° are calculated from these straight

Fig. 2. Plot of α vs T at different temperatures for isothermal decomposition.

lines using least-square method were found to be 0.084, 0.150, 0.280 and 0.460 h⁻¹, respectively. The application of Arrhenius equation with the above results gave the value of activation energy for dehydration to be 94.50 kJ mol⁻¹.

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